

Interaction of Chlorosulphonic Acid with Substituted Amides of Cyanacetic Acid.

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The aim with which this piece of work was undertaken was to study the reactivity of the two hydrogen atoms of a reactive methylene group situated between a cyanogen group and a carbonyl group, as in the case of substituted amides of cyanacetic acid. Attempts were already made to study the reactivity in the case of substituted amides of malonic acid using sulphur monochloride and sulphur dichloride as reagents by Naik (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 379, 1231), by Naik and Avasare (*ibid.*, 1922, 121, 2592, 2595), by Naik and Patel (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 27), by Naik and Jadhav (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 259). Attention is here confined to the study of the interaction of some of the substituted amides of cyanacetic acid using chlorosulphonic acid as the reagent.

It is well-known that chlorosulphonic acid reacts with many organic compounds giving rise to sulphonic derivatives. In fact the reagent has been often employed in the preparation of such compounds (Thorpe's "Dictionary of Applied Chemistry," Vol V. p. 301).

Reference to previous work* clearly shows that chlorosulphonic acid was principally used either in sulphonating aromatic compounds or in the preparation of sulphonyl chlorides. It was expected that here, too, the chlorosulphonic acid would attack the hydrogen atoms of the reactive methylene group and give rise to sulphonic acid derivatives. The experimental evidence recorded in this paper bears this out.

* Hemilian (*Ber.*, 1873, 6, 196); Claessen (*Ber.*, 1881, 14, 307); Hodgkinson and Mathews (*Ber.*, 1888, 16, 1103); Limpricht (*Ber.*, 1885, 18, 2172); Traube (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 1634); Reinhard (*J. pr. Chem.*, 126, 332); Stewart (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2384, 2388); Jacob, Pollak, Fulneggand Reiz (*Monatsh.*, 1926, 46, 383, 397); Krasjinovic (*Ber.*, 1926, 59, 2117, 2719).

An attempt is also made here to shew that the reactivity of these hydrogen atoms depends, in some measure, on the sumtotal negativity of the groups adjoining the reactive methylene group.

Interaction of chlorosulphonic acid with the following substances was studied:—

Cyanacetanilide ;	cyanacet-benzylamide ;
cyanacet- <i>p</i> -toluidide ;	cyanacet- α -naphthylamide ;
cyanacet- <i>o</i> -toluidide ;	cyanacet- β -naphthylamide ;
cyanacet- <i>m</i> -toluidide ;	cyanacet-xylidide (1:4:5).

The first sulphonic acid of the series enumerated above was prepared by reacting cyanacetanilide with chlorosulphonic acid, using dry salicyl chloroform prepared according to Anschütz's method (*Annalen*, 1893, 273, 94 ; *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 3501, 3512), as the medium of interaction. Salicyl chloroform, so prepared, has no action on chlorosulphonic acid at its boiling point.

During the course of the interaction, neither sulphonyl chlorides nor sulphones of the aromatic substituted amides of cyanacetic acid could be isolated. In all the cases sulphonic acid derivatives were obtained and the reagent attacked the methylene group.

Cyanacetanilide, readily interacted with chlorosulphonic acid, thus :

That the constitution assigned to (I) is correct, and that all the sulphoacids, derived from the various amides enumerated above, can be generally so represented follows from the considerations given below.

(1) That the hydrogen atoms eliminated during the course of the interaction are not those which were originally attached to the nucleus, because on hydrolysis with alcoholic caustic potash, *p*-toluidine was obtained as one of the products of hydrolysis from the corresponding sulpho-acid which was derived from cyanacet-*p*-toluidide.

(2) The results of the above hydrolysis also point to the fact that the hydrogen atoms replaced by the sulphonic groups are not those which were originally attached to the nitrogen atoms, as in that case, *p*-toluidine could not have been found as one of the products of hydrolysis.

(3) Further, on attempting to brominate the sulpho-acid (I) the two HSO_3 groups were found to have been replaced by two bromine atoms, as was apparent from subsequent reduction of the di-bromo derivative, both the bromine atoms being easily reduced by Kurt Meyer's method. This clearly proves that the bromine atoms were attached to the methylene carbon atom, and hence, the original sulphonic groups which were replaced by these bromine atoms, also had been attached to the methylene carbon atom.

The three cyanacet-toluidides, cyanacet-benzylamide and cyanacet xylylide and cyanacet-naphthylamides react in a similar manner with chlorosulphonic acid giving analogous sulphonic acid derivatives. But in the cases of the naphthylamides a longer time was required before the reaction was complete.

In relation to the question of the reactivity of the hydrogen atoms of the methylene group with regard to chlorosulphonic acid it may be said that the experimental observations afford a clear evidence that the avidity of the interaction of chlorosulphonic acid with the substituted amides depends on the total negativity of the groups attached to the two remaining valencies of the methylene carbon atom. In the case of cyanacetamide in which one of the valencies of the methylene carbon atom carries the neutral group, ($-\text{CONH}_2$), no reaction takes place. But when the neutral character of this group is disturbed by the entrance in it of a phenyl, a tolyl, a benzyl, a naphthyl or a xylyl group, the reactivity starts.

Although no definite measurements have been made, it is evident from the experiments recorded here, that the rapidity with which the reaction proceeds in these cases depends on the electro-negative character of the groupings attached to the methylene carbon atom. Thus in a series like this—

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|---|---|
| (1) $\text{CN-CH}_2\text{-CONH}_2$, | (2) $\text{CN-CH}_2\text{-CONHC}_6\text{H}_5$, |
| (3) $\text{CN-CH}_2\text{-CONHC}_7\text{H}_7$, | (4) $\text{CN-CH}_2\text{-CONHC}_8\text{H}_3$, |
| (5) $\text{CN-CH}_2\text{-COOEt}$, | |

the reactivity which is absent in (1), starts with (2), and goes on increasing through the series.

The mechanism of the interaction studied here is interesting. In such cases where both the hydrogens of the methylene group are replaced by sulphonic groups when the reaction starts, the substance may be supposed to assume an enolic form (Norris and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1203).

EXPERIMENTAL

Disulphocyanacetanilide.—Cyanacetanilide (3 g.) was mixed in a flask with 25 c.c. of salicyl chloroform and an excess of chlorosulphonic acid (5 g.) was added. A vigorous reaction started with evolution of heat and hydrogen chloride. The flask was kept overnight and refluxed the next day in order to complete the reaction. When the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased and the superfluous chloroform was taken out, 100 c.c. of distilled water were added to the syrupy product and the mixture was boiled. The syrupy mass went into solution and was finally filtered to free it from any unaltered cyanacetanilide. The filtrate deposited shining leaflets, which were washed repeatedly with alcohol in which they were almost insoluble. Finally the product was recrystallised from water. During the course of this investigation it was observed that in all the cases molecular proportions of the reactants did not give a good yield of the final product. An excess of chlorosulphonic acid gave quite satisfactory results, the chance of the amide remaining unreacted being thus completely eliminated.

The pure substance was found to be almost insoluble in alcohol, chloroform, carbon disulphide, carbon tetrachloride, acetone, benzene, toluene, ether and light petroleum. It was extremely soluble in hot water. It had no m.p. but charred above 270°. (Found: S, 16.06; H₂O, 18.3; N, 7.65; Eqv. wt., 197. C₉H₈O₇N₂S₂.4H₂O requires S, 16.32; H₂O, 16.36; N, 7.16 per cent. Equiv. wt., 196.)

In the following preparations 5 g. of chlorosulphonic acid and 3 gms. of the substituted amides were employed. The products were purified as in the previous case. In solubility and other physical properties they resembled disulphocyanacetanilide.

Disulphocyanacet-p-toluidide, crystallised from water in colourless shining leaflets. It had no definite m.p. but darkened and charred at about 270°. Water of crystallisation=2H₂O, of which the compound loses half a molecule of water (2.91 per cent.) at 120°. (Found: S, 17.1. C₁₀H₁₀O₇N₂S₂.2H₂O requires S, 17.29; loss of water, 2.43 per cent.)

Disulphocyanacet-o-toluidide had no definite m.p. but charred at 255-265°. (Found: S, 17.0. $C_{10}H_{10}O_7N_2S_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires S, 17.29 per cent.).

Disulphocyanacet-m-toluidide crystallised in colourless shining scales. It has no definite m.p. but chars between 260° and 270°. (Found: S, 16.96. $C_{10}H_{10}O_7N_2S_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires S, 17.29 per cent.).

Disulphocyanacet-a-naphthylamide crystallised from hot water. It has no definite m.p. but chars between 270° and 280°. (Found: S, 16.46. $C_{13}H_{10}O_7N_2S_2 \cdot H_2O$ requires S, 16.49 per cent.).

Disulphocyanacet-β-naphthylamide was purified by crystallisation from hot water. It formed shining yellowish stout needles, which had no definite m.p. but charred between 270° and 280°. (Found: S, 15.80. $C_{13}H_{10}O_7N_2S_2 \cdot H_2O$ requires S, 16.49 per cent.).

Disulphocyanacetbenzylamide formed colourless plates, which charred between 265° and 275°. (Found: S, 17.3. $C_{10}H_{10}O_7N_2S_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires S, 17.29 per cent.).

Disulphocyanacetxylylidide (1:4:5) crystallised in the form of colourless light shining scales. It has no definite m.p. but chars between 270° and 280°. (Found: S, 17.4. $C_{11}H_{12}O_7N_2S_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires S, 17.48 per cent.).

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